

LEXICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MASS MEDIA IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation: in this article, the study of mass media in English and Uzbek languages and the term mediallynguistics are partially mentioned. Moreover, examples in both languages are given and lexically explained.

Key words: mass media, media, media text, media linguistics, sociolinguistics, ethnolinguistics, ICT, media psychology, lexeme, lexical units, newspaper style, radio, social sites.

INTRODUCTION

It is no exaggeration to say that in the rapidly developing world, all forms of mass media are becoming an integral part of humanity. We can learn the confirmation of our statement from these facts.

Today, the number of Internet users, which has become an important link in the space of receiving and delivering information, is more than 2 billion people. According to data, a person spends more than 40% of his time on mass media during the day.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The term "Mediallynguistics" was formed by analogy with a number of lexical units used to name new academic disciplines emerging at the intersection of sciences – sociolinguistics, ethnolinguistics, media psychology, media economics, etc. This term appeared relatively recently, in 2000. It was used for the first time in the doctoral thesis of T. G. Dobrosklonskaya "Theory and methods of media linguistics". A little earlier, its version in English "media linguistics" appeared, which can be found in the works of British researchers.

The subject of this new science is the study of the activity of language in the field of mass communication, based on the term itself, which combines "mass media" (mass media) and "linguistics". That is, mediallynguistics deals with a comprehensive study of a certain area of speech use – the language of mass media. The legitimacy of emphasizing media linguistics as a new direction of linguistics is connected with the huge role that mass media play for society and the individual. Most of the modern speech practices are used in the field of mass communication. The continuous improvement of information and communication technologies (ICT) leads to a steady increase in the total volume of texts distributed in different national languages in the global information space. At the same time, the subject of media linguistics is not the only discipline that has become a specific field of speech use: the same principle is used to separate another new field of linguistic research – political linguistics into an independent discipline. Its study is the activity of the language in the field of political relations.

RESULTS

While analyzing media lexically, we need to first understand the word lexical. Lexical word (lexeme) is a word with lexical content, studied in the lexicology department of linguistics. Lexical meaning means a set of concepts, emotional-affective colors and stylistic signs expressed by a word. So, concept, emotional-affective color, stylistic sign are called components of lexical meaning.

If words are considered the most important unit of the language, then each unit and sign of the words that we can find in the dictionaries are the specific spiritual aspects of the words. For example, the word “button”, which began to be used in English in the 14th century, belongs to the noun and verb “button (clothing or any technique)” and “to sew a button, to sew has the meaning of “take”. However, this word means “small web ad” in the field of mass media journalism. The word “Button” can also come in the form of “on the button” in the meaning “exactly”.

“PEOPLE HERE ARE LIKE CAPTIVE MONKEYS” (THE NEW YORK TIMES, page A6) – we will analyze the word “captive” used by the author in this sentence “the population is like captive monkeys”. Captive is a word related to the group of nouns and adjectives. An element of simile is used, it is not considered an obsolete word and is used in several speech styles.

Captive

Synonyms	Antonyms
Apprehended, captured, confined, imprisoned, jailed, caught, arrested	free

The dictionary meaning of some words may differ from the context. For example, let’s take the word POWER. “A filing discloses discussions about keeping the former president in power.” (The application revealed the debates about keeping the former president in power.) in this passage, the word “power” comes in the sense of power, in fact, the first dictionary meaning is power, ability, ability, power, etc.

Every period, the lexicon of the newspaper changes due to changes in socio-political or other fields. Such lexicons lead to the formation of unique words, phrases and comments. For example:

➤ In 2020-2021: “coronavirus-crown virus”, “COVID-19”, “mask”, “stay at home”, “price-navo”, “vaccination-vaccine”, “quarantine-isolation”, “30-person wedding”, “third renaissance”, “digitalization”, “distance learning television programs”, “income”, “renewing Uzbekistan”, “medicine”, “open dialogue”, “deputies”, “modernization”, “distance education”, “online communication” and other lexicons were formed.

➤ In 2022: “development strategy”, “new Uzbekistan”, “action strategy”, “social insurance”, “social insurance fund”, “iron notebook”, “youth notebook”, “women’s notebook”, “unified register of social protection”, “micron scar”, “love notebook”, “alphabet of market economy”, “faction”, “strategic reform”, etc.

A word spoken on the radio has a great effect because it is vocal, that is, at the time of its utterance, the speaker has put into it some part of the thoughts that have become a public expression of his feelings. Ladi As the Estonian researcher I. Trickel said, “the live

word is the most complex means of expression on the radio, because thoughts and actions, feelings, character and visual presence must be reflected in it.”

In radio broadcasts, as in other types of mass media, you may come across proverbs, wise words and sayings. For example: “time is the supreme judge”, “mother is a guest in this world, even in her own house”, “even if you stand in front of the ocean, don’t waste a drop of water”, “water is the source of life”, etc.

While listening to the Fergana FM (90.8) radio, this piece caught my attention: “after lunch, the cunning veins are activated.” An element of simile like “cunning veins” draws the listener in and makes him laugh. In this place, it could be said that in the speech of broadcaster, it means “the feeling of rest”, but the broadcast is intended to be more interesting. Or, the sentence “may your face be bright” also creates a change of meaning.

On radio broadcasts, you can hear motivational pieces like: “Look at your watch and keep working, keep walking.”

DISCUSSION

The most widely used global language – English, regardless of the nationality of the representative of the country, uses it and learns it, with its wealth of vocabulary, it does not leave its influence in the age of digital technology. The words that you read, listen to or watch in the media, not only in English, but also in other languages, enter our vocabulary, and we pronounce them in our daily life without hesitation, sometimes even without mistakes. The language does not stay in one place, in the same way or in the same direction, it is definitely enriched with new words that come from other languages.

Social sites have become the most common form of receiving and transmitting information and are an integral part of people’s lives. Social sites bring people closer to long distances, turning them into direct viewers of events happening in any part of the world, and several different actions – phone calls in both audio and visual form, pictures with different backgrounds, emojis, group chats, becoming a huge helper in delivering forums and messages to the masses quickly. It would be safe to say that while you are performing some action on a social site on your phone, thousands of others are acting as a network that can use other functions.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can create new dictionaries, textbooks and training manuals through the lexical analysis of media words, which can be used practically in translation theory and lexicology classes. In teaching and learning English, in addition, knowing the meanings of new words related to the media that may be encountered in the production process or forming their alternatives in our own language, using them in everyday life, will not help to increase understanding.

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